

CHALLENGING ISSUES OF YOUTH CRIME PREVENTION WORLDWIDE

¹Ibraimov Xolboy Ibragimovich, ²Kodirov Obid Safarovich

¹Director of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyoz, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

² Associated professor, Head of the "Psychology" department, doctor of philosophy in psychological sciences, Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10157039>

Abstract. *This article describes the psychological issues of developing ideas about current issues of crime prevention among young people in the world. Currently, aggressive actions of children in their youth and illegal behavior in adolescence are highlighted.*

Keywords: *human rights, security, UN, UNESCO, individual, society, freedom, obligation, socio-economic task, union.*

As an independent subject of international law, Uzbekistan became an equal member of many prestigious international organizations due to independence. In Uzbekistan, the issues of promotion, observance and protection of human rights are considered as one of the priority criteria of the state policy and relations with international partners. Today, a stable political system that meets the criteria of modern democracy and human rights has been formed in our country.

Uzbekistan, in particular, actively cooperates with international and regional organizations such as the United Nations, UNESCO, the International Labor Organization, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, the European Union, the Inter-Parliamentary Union, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, and the Commonwealth of Independent States. set off.

UNICEF made a statement regarding the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the prevention of crime among children and youth¹.

"UNICEF highly appreciates the fact that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan paid special attention to measures to prevent crime among children and youth during his meeting with representatives of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

As a member state of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, Uzbekistan carries out appropriate reforms in the justice system, taking into account the interests of minors in rehabilitation and reintegration processes. The Committee on the Rights of the Child emphasizes the need to look for the social roots of crime. It offers comprehensive crime prevention programs at various levels of the state and community.

It is worth noting that the President called on the relevant state agencies to analyze the crimes committed by young people, determine their causes and strengthen measures to prevent crime.

Children may commit crimes or engage in delinquency for a variety of reasons. According to the results of international studies, such children come from a problematic family environment

¹<https://aniq.uz/yangiliklar/uzbekiston-prezidenti-bmt-bosh-assambleyasining-78-sessiyasida-nutq-suzladi>

with situations such as violence, abuse, neglect and exploitation. Therefore, it is very important to solve the problems of vulnerable children.

Global practice confirms that crime prevention programs are more effective when they are conducted by social protection agencies rather than by law enforcement agencies. UNICEF expresses its readiness to provide technical assistance to relevant ministries and agencies in improving the justice system for children in accordance with international norms and standards”² the statement said.

"Successful prevention of juvenile delinquency requires whole-of-society and state-wide efforts to ensure the well-being of adolescents from early childhood," said Sasha Graumann, UNICEF's Head of the representative office in Uzbekistan. "Young people should play an active role in the life of society they should have opportunities for it, and they should be treated as individuals who contribute to the development of society," he added.

As in many developed countries, fundamental reforms are being implemented in all spheres in our independent Uzbekistan, which has taken a worthy place on the world map. All these reforms raised the human factor to a higher level than ever before, and directly connected his strength, perception, will, potential, mental and spiritual perfection with progress, development and civilization. In this, the problem of a person and his perfection, work on himself, concern for his perfection has become more urgent than ever.

In the address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoev to the Oliy Majlis, "Today, we are moving to the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of state and community life. It's not for nothing. Because in today's fast-paced world, who wins? A country that relies on innovation on a new idea, a new idea, wins. Innovation is the future. If we start building our great future today, we should start it on the basis of innovative ideas and an innovative approach" - clear instructions on the innovative approach to education are given. To know human psychology, to know how to organize one's own development and talent, to ensure optimum study and work suitability at any young age, psychological readiness for various changes, to think and think in a new way, to understand the processes taking place the problems of developing the ability to perceive objectively and accurately are put forward.

Nowadays, the need for psychological knowledge is increasing day by day.

It is very important to acquire psychological knowledge for employees related to law enforcement and legal activities. Psychological knowledge is a component of legal and legal field information. They not only help to solve the special problems that exist for law enforcement and lawyers, but together with the case, they provide the solution of the main criminal legal concepts such as "guilt", "criminal personality", "criminal behavior" from the point of view of legal and legal psychology. 'requires consideration.

Currently, we can see aggressive actions of children in their youth, illegal behavior in adolescence. When studying one third of young people, it was confirmed that 16-17-year-olds have a high tendency to engage in criminal activities.

Currently, the number of crimes committed as a result of carelessness and suicides is increasing with the development of technology. Here we can see the dependence aspects of individual characteristics of a person and careless actions. Such actions are carried out due to indiscipline, carelessness, superficial thinking, laziness, etc.

² <https://kun.uz/02645322>

The need for communication and the desire to have a place in life and to be independent arise only in good conditions and in socially useful activities. If such conditions do not exist, a teenager becomes a member of an informal group of teenagers and meets his needs on the streets to prove his independence and what he is capable of. In such places, his actions turn into antisocial behavior, he becomes interested in drinking, smoking, bad language, hooliganism, and he likes this life.

Making friends with narcotic drugs and alcohol is more common in a person's youth. A person tends to these things more when he is in a state of *anima*. This indicates that people lack socially important ideals, they refuse to fight for their place in real life, to take advantage of opportunities.

In order to get out of the situations and get rid of difficulties, the teenager indulges in drugs and alcoholism. Through narcotics, he becomes a dreamer, these things soothe his heart and give him peace of mind.

In order to pedagogically and psychologically improve the characteristics of adolescent children based on their antisocial behavior, it is necessary to approach each of them individually. As we mentioned above, the formation of the personality of "difficult" teenage children, in most cases, is caused by a turbulent situation in the family. When we look around, people usually join different communities through their common interests and try to fit together there.

During adolescence, the function of endocrine glands also changes, which accelerates sexual maturation. The sensitivity of the central nervous system changes, resulting in vivid feelings. An overactive thyroid gland causes irritability, irritability, and fatigue. Decreasing the inhibition process in the cerebral cortex causes intense emotional experiences, chaos and abnormality appear in behavior. In order to change their behavior for the better, it is necessary to be careful, not to harm their personality, and to give psychological advice necessary for life. Otherwise, cases of hatred of life and suicide attempts can be observed.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga murojatnomasi. 2022 yil 20 dekabr. // www.uza.uz
2. O‘zbekiston Prezidenti BMT Bosh-assambleyasining 78-sessiyasida so‘zladi nutqi. Nyu-York shahridagi Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti bosh qarorgohi. 2023 yil 20 sentyabr — Sputnik. <https://aniq.uz/yangiliklar/>
3. Qodirov O.S. “O‘smirlarda (11-15 yosh) jinoyat motivlari shakllanishining psixodiagnostikasi va psixokorreksiyasi” // Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun tayyorlangan dissertasiya. T.: 2020, - 155 b.
4. Safarovich Q.O. et al. O‘QUVCHILAR XULQ-ATVORI PROFILAKTIKASIDA MAQSADGA YO‘NALTIRILGAN TARBIYAVIY TA‘SIR MODELII //PEDAGOG. – 2023. – T. 6. – №. 2. – C. 382-386.
5. Safarovich Q. O. et al. TARBIYASI QIYIN O‘QUVCHILARNING XULQ-ATVORI BILAN BOG‘LIQ MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISH MASALALARI //PEDAGOG. – 2023. – T. 6. – №. 2. – C. 367-371.
6. Safarovich Q. O. et al. TEENAGER CHILD PSYCHOLOGY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 5. – C. 454-462.
7. Qodirov O.S. Umumiy psixologiya // O‘quv qo‘llanma. - Samarqand, 2022.-250 b.
8. Qodirov O.S., Sh.N.Xotamov. Ijtimoiy psixologiya // Darslik. - Samarqand, 2023.-360 b.

9. Ibraimov Kh. I. Creativity as one of the characteristics of the personality of the future teacher // Science, education and culture. – 2018. – no. 3 (27). - P. 44-46.
10. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
11. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education 1 (2020): 6-15.
12. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
13. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
14. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
15. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
16. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
17. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
18. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
19. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).
20. www.ziyouz.com kutubxonasi.
21. <https://kun.uz/02645322>